

Mineral Composition, Structure and Texture of the Paleogene Period Carbonate Deposits in the Aksokota River Basin

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Abstract: Studying the structure and texture of Aksokota opens a wide way to search for new oil and gas deposits in the current period. The oil and gas industry is developing rapidly. The main future task of geologists working in the oil and gas sector is to contribute to the national economy. It is an independent branch of geotectonics, which studies the structure of the earth's crust and the laws of its development.

Keywords: Aksokota area, section of Paleogene deposits, Paleogene deposits, pelitomorphic dolomite layer, marls, pelitomorphic dolomite layer, dolomite layer, organogenic dolomite layer, carbonate rock layer, maygashkan, organic limestones.

Introduction

Aksokota area is located on the south-western foothills of the Chotkal ridge. Paleogene deposits are developed in the basin of the middle course of the Aksokota River and form the wings of large folded structures of simple structure.

The section of Paleogene deposits was studied in the north-west and south-east flanks of Maygashkan-Surenota anticline and in Teshiktosh field. In all three places, Paleogene deposits lie stratigraphically unconformably parallel to the washed surface of the Late Cretaceous section and are in turn overlain by Neogene Continental molasses. But they differ somewhat in their thickness, lithological composition and other characteristics.

Discussion and Results

Paleogene deposits in the studied area belong to the Aloy and Turkestan suites (layers) of the middle Eocene. The Aloy suite consists mainly of carbonate rocks, and the Turkestan suite consists of terrigenous rocks with small particles. The base section of the Paleogene deposits was established 1.5 km south-west of the village of Gijjal, on the left bank of the Aksoota River. Here, the carbonate rocks of the Aloy suite have formed a steep cliff, and all the layers that make it up are well exposed.

Cross-stratification - the layer is formed from the stratigraphic bottom upwards. Samples were taken from each layer for laboratory analysis. In laboratory conditions, the mineral composition of rocks was studied using transparent slides, X-ray structural and thermal methods.

The lower part of the section is formed by a horizon of fragmented limestones. They lie unconformably on the washed surface of the upper Cretaceous gravelite layer. Carbonate rock fragments consist of pelitomorphic limestones 3-12 cm in size. The filling mass consists of pink marl or clayey limestone. Cracks are found in the limestone horizon. They are filled with diagenetic aragonite. The thickness of such vessels is up to 12 cm. The structure of aragonite is parallel crystal, needle-like. Aggregates are huge crystals.

Pelitomorphic dolomite layer. Dolomite is dense, hard and heavy. The mineral composition consists mainly of dolomite (97%), partially calcite(3%).The crystal size is less than 0.005 mm. The thickness is 2.2m.

A pack of marls. Marls are white uncemented. The carbonate part of the rock consists of dolomite, and the clay part consists of hydromica and montmorillonite. The thickness is 7 m.

Pelitomorphic dolomite layer. Light gray, dense, pelitomorphic structure, massive texture. The shell has a fracture surface. The mineral composition consists mainly of dolomite (95%), calcite (4%), a small amount of quartz (0.5%) and black minerals. The size of dolomite crystals is less than 0.005 mm. Aragonite veins are found in the rock. The thickness is 1.3 m.

Dolomite layer. It has a relatively soft, flour-like structure; light gray, almost white. It contains bivalve mollusk shells. The rock consists of microcrystalline aggregates. The texture is irregularly grainy. Sometimes recrystallized dolomite cells are found. The size of the crystals in them is from 0.007 to 0.01 mm. Dolomite mineral content is 95%, calcite 4.5% and quartz 0.5%. The thickness is 0.8 m.

Organogenic dolomite layer. The layer has a massive structure, 4.1 m thick. The lower part of the layer consists mainly of a collection of bivalve mollusk shells. Towards the upper part of the layer, the number of shells decreases and the organic limestone changes to detrital type. The lower part of the layer consists of micro-grained, pelitomorphic dolomite. Its texture is irregularly grained, recrystallized. The composition consists of 98% dolomite mineral and 1.5% quartz. Accessory minerals are 0.5%. The upper part of the layer consists of pelitomico-grained dolomite aggregates. Foraminifera fossils are observed. Dolomite crystals range in size from 0.005 mm to 0.02 mm and make up 94% of the rock. It contains 3% calcite and 0.5% calcite.

A layer of carbonate rocks. The layer is made of 5-15 cm thick layers that are not visible to the eye. They are light gray, almost white. The outer surface is oval-shaped and has the characteristic of flaking. These rocks are not dense, they have a porous structure. It is much lighter than other layer rocks. The lower part of the layer consists of micro-grained, massive-textured dolomite. The amount of dolomite is 95%, calcite is 3.5-4.0%, and accessory minerals are 1.0-1.5%. In the middle of the layer, dolomite is fine-grained, in some places it is pelitomorphic. The mineral composition consists mainly of dolomite (95%), partly calcite (4%) and quartz (0.5%). The size of quartz grains is 0.30-0.35 mm. The upper part of the layer consists of medium-fine-grained dolomite. The texture is massive. It contains 95% dolomite, 2% calcite, and 1.5-2.0% quartz. The total thickness is 3.5m.

Organogenic dolomite layer. Dolomites are light gray in color. Organic remains are mainly the tar of *Ostrea turkestanensis* Rom shells consists of an irregular arrangement. In addition to them, the remains of round foraminifera with a size of 0.05-0.15 mm are found. Dolomite is the filling mass in the rock. The mineral composition consists of dolomite (96%), calcite (3.0-3.5%) and black minerals (0.5%). The structure is cohesive - lumpy, the texture is massive. Cohesive pieces consist of pelitomorphic aggregates of dolomite forming an isotropic mass of round, oval, irregular and strange shapes with a size of 0.05 to 0.2 mm. The thickness of the layer is 3.2 m.

The upper part of the stratigraphic cross-section consists of a layer consisting of a collection of shells (Fatina) and a horizon of dolomite clays belonging to the Turkestan level. In this section, the rocks of the Turkestan layer were washed away due to their softness, and the

dolomite rocks of the alluvial layer below them were exposed, forming an armored slope in the relief.

On the south-eastern flank of the Maygashkan-Surenota anticline, the thickness of the carbonate deposits of the clay layer is close to that of the above-described section. But it has a significantly higher amount of limestone. In marl rocks, the amount of calcite and dolomite minerals is close to each other. In the Teshiktash section of the Aloy layer, the amount of limestone is even greater. In this section, dolomites do not form separate layers. They are of secondary importance. The main part of the section is made up of organogenic and pelitomorphous limestones and marls. Apart from these, calcarenite sandstones are also significant in this section. They form a separate layer with a thickness of 12 m in the lower part of the section. In calcarenite sandstones, the grains that form the structure consist mainly of limestone and partly of quartz. Lenses and lenticular layers of polymict gravels are found in this pack.

Organogenic limestones are light gray in color and have a massive structure. The thickness of its layers is 2.5-3.1 m. The organic remains consist of scattered large shells of bivalve molluscs.

Pelitomorphous limestones are light gray in color. The mineral composition consists mainly of calcite (85-95%), partially dolomite (10-15%). The size of the crystals is 0.01-0.02 mm. Stylolitic microcuts are widely developed.

Marls contain significantly more calcite than dolomite. The clay part of the rock consists of montmorillonite and hydromica.

The cross-section of the Turkestan plain begins with a horizon consisting of Fatina shells, 2.5 m thick. The filling material is sand. The middle of the section consists of light green glauconite sands with a thickness of 8 m. The section ends with a layer of siltstone reaching fish teeth, coins and phosphorite gravel.

In X-ray diffractograms of samples taken from carbonate rocks, dolomite interlayer distance is 2.86; 2.34; 2.17; 1.99; 1.79; and is diagnosed with basal reflexes of 1.76 Å.

In the diffractograms, calcite is 3.01; 2.02; 1.99 Å and quartz 4.13; 3.32; 2.42; 2.25; It is determined by basal reflexes of 2.10 and 1.79 Å.

In the derivatograms of thermal analysis of samples, two deep endothermic peaks of dolomite are observed at temperatures of 775 and 880°C. The first of them is related to the dissociation of $MgCO_3$ and the second to $CaCO_3$. In limestones, the only deep endothermic peak is observed at 980°C.

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The carbonate rocks of the Paleogene sedimentary layer on the northern-western flank of the Maygashkan-Surenota anticline are mainly composed of dolomites. Dolomite mineral content in them is about 95%. The structure of dolomites is mainly pelitomorphous, partly fine-grained. The texture is spotted.

The amount of dolomites in the cross-section of the Oloy layer decreases in the south-eastern direction, and the amount of limestone increases. In this direction, the amount of terrigenous materials in the cross-section and the size of the structure-forming fragments also increase. This indicates that the sea coast is located in the south-east and the depth of the basin increases towards the north-west.

The formation of dolomites is associated with the combined chemical precipitation of calcium and magnesium carbonates from seawater of shallow and abnormal salinity.

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